

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**THE GREEN ECONOMY: PAVING THE PATH TO SUSTAINABLE PROSPERITY****¹ Samadkulov Mukhammad, ² Turdaliyev Ibrohim**¹ Doctor of Philosophy in Economics, The Yangiyer branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.² 1st year student of the Economics department of the Yangier branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology.**ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: ПРОКЛАДЫВАЯ ПУТЬ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ПРОЦВЕТАНИЮ****¹ Самадқулов Мухаммад, ² Турдалиев Иброхим**¹ Доктор экономических наук, Янгиеровский филиал Ташкентского химико-технологического института.² Студент 1 курса направления "Экономика" Янгиерский филиал Ташкентского химико-технологического института.**YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR FAROVONLIKKA YO'L OCHISH****¹ Samadqulov Muxammad, ² Turdaliyev Ibrohim**¹ Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti Yangiyer filiali iqtisod fanlari doktori.² Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya instituti Yangiyer filiali "Iqtisodiyot" yo'nalishi 1-bosqich talabasi.**abstract**

In an era marked by growing environmental concerns and the urgency to mitigate climate change, the concept of a green economy has emerged as a beacon of hope. The green economy represents a paradigm shift, emphasizing sustainable development, resource efficiency, and social equity. It offers a pathway to reconcile economic growth with environmental protection, creating opportunities for prosperity while safeguarding the planet for future generations.

аннотация

В эпоху растущих экологических проблем и срочности смягчения последствий изменения климата концепция «зеленой» экономики стала маяком надежды. Зеленая экономика представляет собой смену парадигмы, подчеркивающую устойчивое развитие, эффективность использования ресурсов и социальную справедливость. Он предлагает путь к совмещению экономического роста с защитой окружающей среды, создавая возможности для процветания и одновременно сохраняя планету для будущих поколений.

annotatsiya

Atrof-muhit muammolari va iqlim o'zgarishini yumshatishning dolzarbligi bilan ajralib turadigan davrda yashil iqtisodiyot tushunchasi umid chirog'i sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Yashil iqtisodiyot barqaror rivojlanish, resurslar samaradorligi va ijtimoiy tenglikni ta'kidlab, paradigma o'zgarishini ifodalaydi. U iqtisodiy o'sishni atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish bilan uyg'unlashtirish yo'lini taklif qiladi, farovonlik uchun imkoniyatlar yaratadi va kelajak avlodlar uchun sayyorani himoya qiladi.

Keywords:

resource, ecological, ecosystem, purification, renewable, biodiversity.

Ключевые слова:

ресурс, экологический, экосистема, очистка, возобновляемые источники энергии, биоразнообразие.

Kalit so'zlar:

resurs, ekologik, ekotizim, tozalash, qayta tiklanadigan, biologik xilma-xillik.

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Foundations of the Green Economy

At its core, the green economy seeks to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation. Traditional economic models often prioritize short-term gains at the expense of long-term sustainability. However, the green economy recognizes that continued exploitation of natural resources is not viable in the face of ecological limits and climate change.

Key principles of the green economy include:

1. **Resource Efficiency:** Maximizing the use of renewable resources and minimizing waste generation are central tenets of the green economy. This involves adopting sustainable production and consumption patterns, promoting recycling and circular economy practices, and reducing reliance on finite resources.

2. **Renewable Energy:** Transitioning towards renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power is essential for reducing carbon emissions and mitigating climate change. Investing in renewable energy infrastructure not only reduces dependency on fossil fuels but also creates new job opportunities and enhances energy security.

3. **Conservation and Biodiversity:** Protecting ecosystems, conserving biodiversity, and restoring degraded lands are integral components of the green economy. Preserving natural habitats not only supports wildlife and ecological balance but also provides essential

ecosystem services such as clean air, water purification, and climate regulation.

4. **Social Equity:** The green economy prioritizes inclusivity and social equity, ensuring that the benefits of sustainable development are shared equitably among all segments of society. This involves creating green jobs, promoting fair labor practices, and addressing disparities in access to resources and opportunities.

Benefits of Embracing the Green Economy

Embracing the principles of the green economy offers a multitude of benefits, ranging from environmental preservation to economic resilience:

1. **Environmental Sustainability:** By reducing environmental degradation and carbon emissions, the green economy helps safeguard ecosystems, mitigate climate change, and preserve natural resources for future generations.

2. **Economic Growth:** Contrary to the misconception that environmental protection stifles economic growth, the green economy fosters innovation, stimulates investment in clean technologies, and creates new markets and industries. Studies have shown that investments in renewable energy and energy efficiency can yield significant economic returns while reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

3. **Job Creation:** The transition to a green economy generates employment opportunities across various sectors, including renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, green construction, and waste

management. These green jobs not only offer meaningful work but also contribute to local economies and community development.

4. Resilience and Adaptation: Building resilience to environmental shocks and climate change is crucial for long-term prosperity. The green economy promotes adaptive strategies such as sustainable land management, climate-resilient infrastructure, and disaster preparedness, enhancing the resilience of communities and economies.

Challenges and Opportunities

Despite its potential, the transition to a green economy is not without challenges. Resistance from vested interests, lack of political will, and financial barriers often hinder progress. Additionally, ensuring a just transition for workers in carbon-intensive industries and addressing social inequalities remain significant challenges. However, these challenges also present opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and systemic change. Governments, businesses, civil society, and individuals all have a role to play in advancing the green economy agenda. Policy interventions, technological innovations, financial incentives, and public awareness campaigns are essential tools for accelerating the transition towards sustainability.

Conclusion

The green economy represents a bold vision for the future—a future where economic prosperity goes hand in hand with environmental stewardship and social justice. By embracing the principles of

sustainability, resource efficiency, and inclusivity, we can create a world where prosperity is not at the expense of the planet but in harmony with it. The time to act is now, and the transition to a green economy offers a roadmap to a more sustainable and equitable future for all.

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